

CORPORATE BUDGET AS A MANAGEMENT CONTROL INSTRUMENT IN INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

This paper addresses the issue of corporate budgeting as a management control instrument in industry. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that it clarifies to the general public that cost accounting, combined with the industrial production control system, represents lower risk levels and greater insight into the business, which implies safer and more accurate decision-making, especially regarding future investments. The general objective adopted was to understand how corporate budgeting can be used as an effective management control instrument in industry. The specific objectives are to present the concept of budgeting and discuss the concept of cost as an accounting tool for industrial management. The need to budget is inherent to the existence of any business, but the task of doing so falls to professionals working in the accounting system, who will have the freedom to create reliable reports that will serve as instruments for managers to manage prices, investments, markets and acquisitions, with greater immediate decision-making power. The corporate budget is an indispensable tool for managers, executives, entrepreneurs and investors, because it enables decision-making with greater caution and security regarding the returns applied. The conclusions reached after carrying out this work are that the Accountant should be to all branches, departments and sectors of production, highlighting investments when necessary and encouraging good management of the entire production, as well as the factual presentation that cost attentive management and budget management represent roles of the highest relevance in corporate decision-making.

Keywords: Corporate budget. Cost management. Control management in industry.

INTRODUCTION

Managing an industry is a highly complex factor, especially in the factor that refers to the prices of products made available to retailers. In the secondary sector, which is where the

raw material is processed, there is a whole contingency of meeting the final quality requirement that invariably depends on the quality of the product that is received for processing. What this implies today for the survival of the company that operates in industrial production is that, contrary to what one might think, superior quality of the raw material implies greater added value, therefore, a higher price paid, which will directly affect the final costs. It does not always work that way, because the industrial sector has its own logic of operation, such as specific machinery, selection sector, product preparation, testing sector, among others.

When an industry decides to invest in improving its product, it has to invest in two other sectors, the first of which is the quality of the raw material, which will imply an increase in costs, but this does not mean that it can increase the value of its final product, because at the same time, it can invest in higher production machines, market expansion and with this, what would be disadvantageous, becomes a management investment process that results in excellent results.

It is important to note that linking the increase in production costs in a given industry sector/department is not always related to the increase in retail prices. It is important to clarify that within the industry, there are several segments of production and processing of raw materials. Therefore, the professional responsible for Accounting must act to determine the value of the production cost in each of these areas, so that he or she can ultimately determine what the final result of the real value of the product offered would be, and can intervene in the preparation of reliable reports that will assist in the business management of production.

In this sense, Toledo (1997 *apud* VILANONA and RIBEIRO, 2011, p. 6) argues that “being aware of the unit cost, although necessary, is not enough; it is necessary to have a global vision of the company. Above all, cost is information, and should be used by managers who have knowledge about what cost is, how it was obtained and for what purpose.”

According to Lunkes (2003), the need to budget is as old as humanity. Cavemen needed to anticipate the need for food during the long winters, and so they developed ancient budgeting practices. When the process of civilization came, questions of costs arose, because there was a need to have seeds for the next harvests and with the surplus, exchanges could be made using equivalent values. Therefore, it was necessary to know how much it had cost to produce a unit of each thing, so that neither party would be harmed in the negotiation.

More specifically, regarding cost control, its most important mission is to provide reliable data for establishing standards, budgets and other forms of forecasting, which allows managers to prepare a forecasting agenda, regarding prices, investments, raw material acquisitions, impact on production volume (increase or reduction). In a subsequent stage, it

serves to monitor events, enabling comparison with previously defined values, projecting expenses and/or investments in future productions (VILANOVA and RIBEIRO, 2011).

In an attempt to explain the concept of budget, Andrade (2020, p. 10) argues that this is,

A formal quantitative expression that starts from past behavior and looks at possible future changes, quantifying, in economic and financial terms, the company's activities. It is a forecast, a target according to which decisions will be made.

It can be inferred from this statement that the budget is the result of exhaustive work by those responsible for the company's accounting activities, aiming to enable the company to make the most accurate decisions and with greater confidence in the results to which its investments are applied.

This paper seeks to clarify that, when working with process management in mind, every detail must be considered, understanding that, in this process, the Accountant is not only dealing with final accounting, but also seeking to understand the details of development, in order to increase production, enabling effective results to be achieved. The general objective was to understand how the corporate budget can be used as an effective instrument for control management in the industry. The specific objectives are to present the concept of budget and discuss the concept of cost as an accounting tool for industrial management.

BUDGET CONCEPT

Budget is the monetary expression of an operational plan, which constitutes the final stage of the planning process, where, through it, the Accountant has the opportunity to provide a commitment to implementation. Therefore, it is an instrument for monitoring and continuously evaluating the performance of activities and departments, allowing the preparation of production costs with greater security (ANDRADE, 2020).

In this author's view, the usefulness of the budget can be interpreted in the following terms:

Specify the organization's next objectives; prepare short-term plans; estimate the resources associated with the plans; establish an investment plan; develop a production and purchasing plan; predict the need for MOD and prepare it; establish financial budgets; adjust the overall budget; give detailed form to the strategic plan in the form of values; assist in the coordination of the organization's various activities; define executives' responsibilities, authorize the spending limits they can make and inform them of the performance expected of them; intervene to ratify the plans; measure and evaluate the

company's performance; monitor the strategy, verify its degree of success and take corrective action (ANDRADE, 2020, p. 15-16).

It can be inferred here that there are several functions and their application will depend on a set of actions and data that the company has been using as a way of recording and taking care of its operations. What has also been clarified is that such functions require everyone to be proactive within the organization, from the base employees to the executives.

Welsch (1983) defines a budget as an administrative plan that covers all phases of operations for a defined future period. It is the formal expression of the policies, plans, objectives and goals established by senior management for the company as a whole, as well as for one of its subdivisions. Its objective is to monitor the company's performance and ensure that deviations are analyzed and adequately controlled, and for this purpose, daily monitoring of the budget is necessary.

There is a belief that,

The corporate budget is a powerful and irreplaceable tool in the business world. (...) The challenge of globalization and even the tactical need to adapt to the market arise so frequently that it becomes very difficult to understand how to manage a business without a tool that allows managers to have adequate guidance. [*However*], although important, planning and controlling the business, in many companies, consists of actions that are not yet adequately understood by executives. This difficulty is perceived in organized companies that had a tradition in preparing and managing their business plan. It is interesting to note that in some cases, the availability of a certain operating mode would make the company's executives believe that, in a certain way, it would solve the problems presented in their daily management. It is like imagining that by having a budget system in the company, it could guarantee the success of the planning process, as well as, through it, achieve the desired success (ZACHARIAS, 2018, p. 05).

The budget adds fast and efficient information to the industry's economic and accounting planning. Even though its implementation may seem complex, because when it proposes to elect each production sector as an autonomous link that is responsible for part of the company's profitability, it can bring benefits that will contribute to reducing the margin of error, information redundancy and profit maximization (MAIA et al, 2009), and also helping to define the final prices for the retailer, making the product more competitive.

Thus, it can be defined that,

The budget is a planning and control instrument that becomes of great relevance for companies, as it establishes in advance the actions to be executed and the resources that will be spent, that is, the company measures how much it wants to produce to achieve the proposed revenue and from there it has to analyze which resources it will make available so that it can produce what is

desired, this means that it needs to know what the cost will be with labor, raw materials and whether it will need to invest in fixed assets (MAIA et al, 2009, p. 07).

This statement clearly shows that it is impossible to manage any enterprise, especially in the industrial sector, without a budgetary policy based on solid data, because just as investments in the wrong sectors are causes of unnecessary risk, the practice of investing in sectors that do not require such processes is incurring the risk of insolvency. Therefore, the technical team, when preparing basic budgets, must start from serious studies and incisive analyses.

Complementing this idea, Frezatti (2007) argues that the budget is the financial plan to implement the company's strategy for a given fiscal year. It is more than a simple estimate, as it must be based on the managers' commitment in terms of goals to be achieved.

COST CONCEPT

Cost can be understood as the economic expense involved in manufacturing a given product or providing a service. By establishing the cost of production, it is possible to determine the retail price of the good in question (the retail price is the sum of the cost plus the profit). Expanding on this idea, the cost of a product is made up of the price of the raw material, the price of the direct labor used in its production, the price of the direct and indirect labor used to operate the company, and the cost of amortizing the machinery and buildings.

In the case of industry, production costs are thought of and analyzed differently from a retail company, which is already part of the tertiary sector and does not involve the origin of its materials in its planning.

In industry, there are several sectors that respond [*almost*] independently for their production conditions, with varying costs at each stage. In this regard, the Accountant needs to establish evaluation parameters for each department and, in the end, detecting bottlenecks, develop general cost reduction policies together with management.

Menezes (2009, p. 427) highlights that,

Cost is the sum of the expenses incurred and necessary for the acquisition, conversion and other procedures necessary to bring the inventories to their current condition and location and includes all expenses incurred in their acquisition or production, in order to put them in a condition to be sold, transformed, used in the preparation of products or in the provision of services that are part of the corporate purpose of the entity [...]. Thus, cost is the amount spent on goods and services for the production of other goods and services.

With regard specifically to cost classification, Wernke (2004) mentions that among the various classifications existing in the accounting literature, those with the greatest managerial applicability are those that segregate costs in terms of decision-making, being classified as relevant and non-relevant; in terms of identification, as direct and indirect costs; and in terms of the volume produced, costs can be classified as variable or fixed.

Such classifications cannot be taken as limiting decision-making actions, because they go far beyond this, allowing managers to know when to enter a new market, expand business, leave markets that are proving unproductive and even make internal adjustments, such as acquiring machinery, source of raw material supply, as occurred with companies in the veterinary pharmaceutical sector that chose, in the mid-1990s, to change their suppliers of *Streptomyces avermitilis* to China, because the price was twenty times cheaper and with the same quality.

Wernke (2004) defines relevant costs as those that change depending on the decision made and that are considered as a subsidy in the decision-making process, while non-relevant costs are those that are independent of the decision made and that do not need to be considered in this process (Silva et al, 2012).

Regarding direct costs Wernke (2004) and Duboys, Kulpa and Souza (2009), cited by Silva et al (2012, p. 04),

They are defined as expenses that can be easily allocated to the units produced, i.e., they can be identified as belonging to a given product without the need for apportionment (a device used to distribute costs that cannot be determined objectively and safely to which products they refer). Conversely, indirect costs are expenses that cannot be allocated objectively or directly to products or services. They are difficult to measure and appropriate, thus requiring the use of apportionment criteria to appropriate them.

It is important to keep in mind that the industry works with very high production volumes and that there are residues that are subject to a whole range of pragmatic legislation; for this reason, the Accountant must be aware that all the management of this production surplus has a separate cost and cannot be treated as a simple *production residue*. Therefore, it is clear that the industrial sector has specificities that are strictly different from the retail sector, and this is the responsibility of the Accounting professional to ensure that they do not apply views from different fields to different phases of a given product, generating false positive reports.

Mendes (2017) clarifies that the budget process requires data, especially accounting data. And, it must be a complete information system that enables planning with truthfulness, reliable data that corresponds to reality. Thus,

The budget is a fundamental instrument for the company, regardless of its size and sector of activity, as it is a strategic plan that establishes goals for a given period, leading the company to its objectives. When a company chooses to prepare a budget, in addition to collecting and grouping data, it is necessary to monitor budget variations on a monthly basis (CREMONEZZI et al., 2010, p. 2).

It should be noted that, based on this heading, the preparation of documents must be reliable and represent the procedural, financial and market reality in which the company operates.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

When discussing the issue of applying Cost Accounting to industrial management, the aim is to optimize specific production sectors, ranging from the acquisition of raw materials to the treatment of waste produced. Based on reliable reports, the company can choose to carry it out with its own resources or outsource the action. In this regard, industrial management aims to optimize financial, material and information flows by applying gap detection methodologies and implementing improvement actions in the industrial areas of companies.

Berliner (1992, p. 88) states that the interest in preparing budgetary costs in industries refers to:

Eliminate costs that do not add value; account for costs based on activities; use the target cost concept; take into account the product life cycle in its cost; evaluate performance, measure productivity, quality, deadlines; manage investments, calculate project profitability.

In line with the thinking presented above, it is clear that detailed knowledge of Accounting and Cost Management principles provides direct gains to those companies that adhere to detailed treatment of their processes, because they begin to determine each step to be developed and how they can add value to what they produce, without this affecting the scale of production and the quality of the product, what they can actually process and what is more viable to outsource and remain that way, without attempting to enter a market that is sometimes complex.

In Martins's view (2003, p. 11),

A company, as a real asset, is a means of generating wealth for its owners - shareholders or unitholders. Regardless of the mission, purpose or business philosophy, in a capitalist society the willingness to invest is stimulated by expected cash flows, that is, by the prospect of gains that will be generated for investors in both the short and long term.

Taking this principle as the guiding principle of business management, costs and budgets are tangible instruments that will demonstrate the ability of such an organization, company or industry to be profitable and attractive to investors. This is a North American precept of thought, in which the idea of corporate social responsibility does not exist and what it aims at is, definitively, the profit returned on the invested capital. Hence, the greatest investment of studies in this field is more in-depth and more detailed.

An example will be given that occurred with a regional company, the now defunct Realeza Agricultural Cooperative – COOPAREAL. This company worked with the collection of *raw milk*, basic industrial processing and sold its surplus milk. At a certain point, its president was advised to acquire a machine that pasteurized milk with greater processing speed, lower cost and adding quality to it, which would automatically add value to the final product.

It did not happen this way, because the high acquisition cost of the machine required it to operate 24 hours a day and due to the volume of milk they collected from their suppliers, it was idle 9 hours a day and this opportunity cost represented financial ruin.

There was a lack of management, because the company could offer its services to others or the company itself could sublet or outsource such action. As no attention was paid to this occurrence, the final solution was bankruptcy, because the costs made the entire operation unviable, making the business unsustainable, given that it had to lower the prices of raw materials and, as a result, competitors gained ground.

Mendes (2017, pp. 15-16) states that,

Preparing budgets requires a period of preparation and conflict management, because often, in order to modify a budget for a given area, it may necessarily mean having to modify the budget for another area, which may or may not please the managers involved. Therefore, at the end of the process, the budgets need to be aligned, so that the overall budget is realistic and achievable.

By integration, we understand here the correct conjunction of data, the faithful dimension of the same, showing the sectors in harmony and responses that allow managers to make decisions and investors, both to inject resources into the company and also to withdraw their investments from it.

CONCLUSION

Through this study it was possible to understand that industrial costs are wide-ranging and there is a pressing need for the Accountant to be attentive to all branches, departments and

sectors of production, emphasizing investments when necessary and encouraging good management of all production, through reliable reports so that there is no risk of bankruptcy, in extreme cases, and losses, due to lack of good business management.

The budgetary issue represents a very broad part of accounting work, in which studies and analyses are guiding milestones so that managers, executives and investors can carry out their work, according to the functions that are the responsibility of each one.

In the example reported above, what was missing was efficient budget management in which problems could be anticipated and even strategic actions could be considered, around the acquisition of equipment, perhaps with smaller production dimensions and that would meet the company's limits.

The conclusion reached, after carrying out the studies and analyzing the content explored, is that cost management and budget management play roles of the highest relevance in business decision-making.

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